

BEEP BEEP BEEP: STEERING THE PERCEPTION OF JEEPNEY DRIVERS TOWARDS JEEPNEY MODERNIZATION

Mara Raine P. Cunanan ¹, Joshua L. Rosel ¹, Arelly Angel O. Balilo ¹, Louie C. Lugue Jr.¹, Angelo P. Sandot ¹, Renz M. Pamintuan ¹, Sean Danielle D. David ¹, John Louise M. Marcaida², Dexk Michael N. Tayag²

¹ Senior High School Department, Our Lady of Fatima University, Philippines

² Department of Physical Education, Our Lady of Fatima University, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13346354>

ABSTRACT

To strengthen and develop the PUVM, the study attempts to ascertain the views and opinions of jeepney drivers regarding public utility vehicle modernization. This qualitative-phenomenological study included a complete list of the responses of Jeepney drivers in the Bulaon-San Fernando Jeep Terminal who voluntarily participated in this qualitative research (30) by responding to a semi-structured questionnaire. This open-ended and closed-ended questionnaire analyses the perceptions of the jeepney drivers and the challenges of the PUVM to the jeepney drivers. The study employed manual coding to carry out Braun and Clarke's thematic analysis approach. Three themes emerged from the research that shed light on the attitudes and views of jeepney drivers regarding PUVM and its impact on them: (1) preserving cultural heritage and economic resilience: The Jeepney Industry's Struggle Against Modernization; (2) fare adjustments and passenger competition in Jeepney Modernization; and (3) daily impacts: the Effect of PUVM on Jeepney Drivers Daily Lives. The findings of this study may wake people up, especially the higher-ups, to what is happening to the jeepney drivers towards the PUVM. In addition, it may enhance the PUVM to improve and be a better program for everyone, and it may also raise social awareness among the people.

Keywords: *jeepney modernization program, public transportation system, public utility vehicle modernization, jeepney drivers, social awareness*

INTRODUCTION

Conventional jeepneys are a big part of our everyday transportation. After World War II, US Forces abandoned their military jeeps, the Filipinos combined spare components from repurposed machines to build a maximum commuter car that could hold six people. Meanwhile, in 2017 the Department of Transportation began implementing the jeepney refurbishment plans. The widespread use of conventional transportation is to be replaced by safer, more contemporary vehicles that will have a smaller negative impact on the environment. The program's objective is to solve the issues including outdated technology, safety concerns, and environmental effects by incorporating elements such as emission compliance and upgraded safety measures.

The Philippine government is pursuing sustainable growth solutions in response to growing environmental concerns. As stated by Atos et al. (2021), "the suggestion to update the nation's iconic symbol, the jeepney." Incorporating input from commuters, operators, and drivers had a major impact on modernizing the fleet of jeepneys. The Jeepney Modernization Program has encountered various obstacles. As mentioned by Clavecillas (2017), these replacements, the plan was for jeepneys to replace the 15 years or older, which has an impact on operators and drivers who have spent the most time working in the field. Correspondingly, Manuel (2020) stated that the quantity of the nation's jeepney fleet and its expensive operators and the replacement will be covered by the drivers. However, the implementation of the program was delayed. According to Biona et al. (2023) By 2020, the Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program (PUVMP) was supposed to be finished. However, due to the COVID-19 outbreak and the protests by Philippine transport groups in March 2023, the government decided to postpone the franchise consolidation date to December 31, 2023. The biggest worry for these roadmasters is their source of income because they fear that the replacement of jeepneys' high cost will force them with nothing but debt and a diminished standard of living, adding to their already challenging lives.

Knowledge is the main benefit of raising awareness. As stated by Zagzebski (2017), knowledge is a highly respected state that entails cognitive engagement with reality. The researchers can help people acknowledge and hear the voices and perceptions of beloved jeepney drivers who've been there since the start and have become a part of our culture toward jeepney modernization. A special focus on socialization will be placed on this study because the goal is to observe, explore, and assess the viewpoints of jeepney drivers regarding the modernization project. Social awareness helps people understand, as they grow older, how they fit into and contribute to society and the environment, as well as how we get the things we need from them. As stated by Kaiser (2022), to create vibrant, healthy relationships and make moral decisions, people must develop social awareness, also known as socialization. Since social awareness is a crucial ability for enhancing interpersonal interactions and communication, it can help us deal with problems and challenges like how drivers view the modernization of the jeepney. The researchers conducted this study to educate people on a wider scale about the reality of what their nation is experiencing regarding modernizing jeepneys. This study's findings,

aims to promote greater awareness and understanding of the challenges and needs faced by jeepney drivers, which would eventually result in more productive discussions and decisions regarding transportation regulations.

Modernized Jeepneys and the Transformation of Commuting Experiences

In an era marked by rapid technological advances, modernized jeepneys are not just transforming the way we commute but also contributing to broader and more efficient public transportation. According to the Department of Science and Technology (DOST), the new jeepney's features, which include digital route signs, CCTV cameras, dash cams, PUV stop buttons, rear emergency doors, cashless payment systems, and public speaker systems, are all designed with the safety and comfort of its passengers in mind. With better safety features and more comfort for passengers, these modernized jeepneys are reshaping the commuting experience. Moreover, the focus on making transportation accessible ensures that everyone, including those with disabilities, can easily use public transit systems. Through working together, using technology, and making designs that work for everyone, the objective is to create a connected, accessible, and safer experience for all. The Land Transportation Franchising and Regulatory Board (LTFRB) mentioned that the program seeks to enhance the quality of life for all citizens in the Philippines by offering a safer, more efficient, reliable, convenient, cost-effective, eco-friendly, and sustainable transportation system nationwide.

Exploring the Influence of Jeepney Vehicles impact on Filipino Culture

The jeepney vehicle in the Philippines has been a trademark for Filipinos. They use this vehicle for daily transportation. For those who budget their money on transportation, riding a jeepney saves them a lot of money, especially students, senior citizens, and PWDs, because of the discounts. As mentioned by Savilla et al. (2023), jeepneys are iconic images of the Philippines that represent the people's inventiveness. The development of these vibrant public transportation options began in the 1950s. After World War II, the American troops departed the Philippines, leaving behind many vehicles. The Philippines has been known for its colorful, eye-catching, and creative jeepneys, which became one of their cultures. From the jeepney itself to the hardworking drivers, driving a jeepney helps them find a good job and serve people. Every jeepney vehicle can help other people show their creativity by designing, enhancing, and detailing their vehicles.

As of today, these jeepneys are being phased out and modified to an e-jeep. According to Estipular (2020), "The Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program (PUVMP)" was put into effect and unveiled in 2017 to completely change the Philippines' public transportation system. The primary means of transportation for Filipinos is jeepneys. To preserve Philippine culture or tradition, modernized jeepneys should be designed like the modern ones. As said by Zulueta et al. (2024), "It is advised to maintain cultural distinctiveness by designing modern jeepneys to resemble traditional jeepneys to attract commuters from the Philippines." The higher-ups should also consider preserving the culture of the Philippines before phasing out the traditional jeepneys because, as said by Landayan et al. (2024), "the jeepney is a painting that captures the essence of Filipino culture, not just

a means of transportation. Locals quickly transformed the public utility cars into movable artworks. Artists began painting vivid murals, elaborate patterns, and even ironic sayings on jeepneys, transforming them into moving works of art.”

Alterations of Public Transport from Traditional to Modern

In the Philippines, the iconic jeepney reigns supreme as the quintessential mode of public transportation, catering to the daily commuting needs of a significant portion of the population Baluyot et al. (2017). However, recognizing the pressing need for a shift towards sustainability and efficiency in the transport sector, the government has embarked on a transformative journey with the launch of the Public Utility Vehicle (PUV) Modernization Program. As stated by Castro (2019), This initiative places a spotlight on the introduction of updated diesel and electric jeepneys, commonly referred to as e-jeepneys, signalling a pivotal step towards fostering a greener and more sustainable public transportation landscape.

However, despite the undeniable potential for positive change, the implementation of the PUVM modernization program encounters substantial resistance from various stakeholders within the transportation sector. Foremost among these dissenting voices are transportation associations, whose opposition is primarily fuelled by apprehensions surrounding investment risks and financial burdens associated with the transition. According to Baracao et al. (2023), these concerns highlight the inherent challenges and complexities involved in effecting a comprehensive overhaul of the existing transportation infrastructure.

Research Questions

The general objective of this study is to uncover the perception of jeepney drivers toward the Jeepney Modernization Program. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following:

1. What is the perspective of jeepney drivers in the Jeepney Modernization Program?
2. How does the jeepney modernization program affect the transportation system?
3. How are the jeepney drivers going to handle this upgrading program for jeepney

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized qualitative research to present the framework and to discern and perceive the perceptions of jeepney drivers to PUVM. Also, to provide an in-depth analysis and understanding of the perception of jeepney drivers in Bulaon-San Fernando Terminal about the PUVM. Hennink et al. (2020) stated that qualitative research is a methodology that enables the detailed examination of people's experiences using a particular set of research techniques, including life histories or biographies, in-depth interviews, focus groups, observation, content analysis, and visual aids. Additionally, phenomenological methods apply wherein this approach investigates the everyday

experiences of human beings while suspending the researchers' preconceived assumptions about the phenomenon. In the lens of Quinney et al. (2016), understanding and exploring the substance of a human experience, as well as starting a conversation with the subject, are the main goals of phenomenological research. In terms of participants in this study. The study focused on regular jeepney drivers at the San Fernando Jeep terminal in Bulaon, with thirty drivers participating voluntarily. The researcher used purposive sampling, a method where participants are selected based on specific criteria, as defined by Obilor (2023), to ensure relevance and practicality. This approach was chosen to capture detailed and nuanced insights from drivers directly at the terminal. Researchers intentionally selected individuals using purposive sampling. Using this method and its practicality in select individuals, researchers identified their targeted jeepney driver participants directly at their designated terminal.

In collecting data from participants. The researchers utilized a semi-structured interview following the study objective. The semi-structured interview was conducted via face-to-face interaction. In the collection of data, the researchers respectfully addressed the participants, asking for permission to conduct interviews and outlining the goal of the study. To promote comfort, they utilized the participants' preferred language and thoughtfully selected phrases. To ensure correct documentation, permission was also sought to record responses. All information gathered for this study will be kept private and confidentiality by the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The data generated from the participant replies was methodologically collected, transcribed, structured, analysed, and appraised using the Thematic Analysis Method of Braun and Clarke (2006), yielding insightful results. According to Braun and Clarke (2006), this method is frequently used in qualitative research because it provides insightful and comprehensive results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The methods described by Braun and Clarke (2006) are used in this study to present a thorough thematic interpretation of the results obtained from theme analysis. To completely comprehend the idea of the study, an intensive and meticulous explanation was also provided to give the derived themes and subthemes their underlying qualities and meanings.

Theme 1: Preserving Cultural Heritage and Economic Resilience: The Jeepney Industry's Struggle Against Modernization

The Jeepney Industry's Struggle Against Modernization encapsulates a poignant narrative at the intersection of tradition and progress. Jeepneys, iconic symbols deeply embedded in the country's cultural fabric, emerged from surplus military jeeps post-World War II, evolving into colorful manifestations of Filipino resourcefulness and resilience. However, as modernization efforts seek to enhance safety, reduce emissions, and improve efficiency, the very essence of the jeepney industry and the livelihoods it sustains

face unprecedented challenges. As stated by Mateo-Babiano (2020), this theme delves into the complex dialogue surrounding the preservation of cultural heritage amidst rapid technological advancement, raising pivotal questions about inclusivity, governmental support, and the imperative of finding innovative solutions that honor tradition while embracing progress. In addition, Andalecio (2020) notes that in many Philippine cities, jeepneys—paratransit vehicles—account for most urban transportation. 90% of the approximately 179,000 jeepneys in use are fifteen years of age or older. But there are a lot more problems along the way. To address this, the government unveiled a historic bill creating the Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program (PUVMP), a ground-breaking, expansive initiative focused mostly on land-based public transit, the majority of which is jeepneys.

Subtheme 1.1 Financial Strain and Resistance to Modernization in the Jeepney Industry.

This sub-theme emerges as the result of the perspective of jeepney drivers towards the execution of the jeepney modernization program. According to Andelancio et al (2020), Jeepney drivers face financial challenges during the jeepney modernization program, The implementation of the program involves phasing out old regular jeepneys and replacing them with modernized jeepneys, which requires drivers to invest in new vehicles. However, the cost of acquiring modernized jeepneys poses a significant financial burden for drivers, as they may not have the necessary funds to purchase these vehicles. In addition, Dimalanta et al (2019) stated Jeepney drivers typically earn around 500 pesos per day in gross revenue. Meanwhile, jeepney operators see a driver typically earning between P2,500 and P3,000. The high cost of modern jeepneys far surpasses the financial capacity of both drivers and operators, creating a significant financial burden. The Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program (PUVMP) of the government offers finance packages through the Development Bank of the Philippines (DBP) and Land Bank of the Philippines (Landbank) to ease the transition to new jeepneys. However, given the high cost of modern jeepneys and the financial limitations of many drivers and operators, the program's current funding might be insufficient. Increasing the available funds or exploring alternative financing options could help bridge this gap. These financial difficulties may make it more difficult for the jeepney modernization initiative to be implemented successfully and may necessitate government intervention to support and aid drivers.

Subtheme 1.2 Preserving Cultural Heritage and Unique Identity

This sub-theme comes out as an outcome of jeepney drivers' deep attachment to the traditional jeepney as a symbol of Filipino identity. Cerio (2017) mentioned that as the "moving icon of Philippine culture," the jeepney has not only become a common sight on the country's streets but has also become ingrained in Filipino identity, culture, and values. The jeepney represents the ingenuity, originality, talent, and business acumen of the Filipino people. Furthermore, the jeepney is more than just a means of transit; it contains history, artistry, and community. As stated by Solina (2023), the Philippine transportation system is known for its jeepneys. The jeepney, which has been a means

of transportation for the Filipino people since the mid-1900s, is well-known for its vibrant, imaginative, and locally inspired patterns.

Additionally, according to Gatarin (2024), preserving traditional jeepneys is essential for safeguarding the unique character and cultural heritage of the Philippines. Having provided transportation for the public since the end of World War II, these public utility vehicles (PUVs) are now recognized as significant cultural symbols on Filipino streets. Ranis et al. (2021) mentioned that, as the "Kings of the Road," jeepneys are the main form of transportation used by most Filipinos daily. Across cities throughout the Philippines, public transit, facilitated by jeepneys, provides crucial access to employment opportunities, essential resources, healthcare services, and recreational activities. Due to the lowest fare, it helps commuters as well as those who own a vehicle. Jeepneys are significant in Filipino cultures as both a means of transportation and an iconic object. These recognizable vehicles represent the culture and heritage of Filipino communities and are more than just a means of transportation.

Subtheme 1.3 The Voices of Jeepney Drivers Against Modernization

This sub-theme emerged because of the jeepney driver's perceptions against jeepney modernization. As stated by Mendoza (2021), the government's modernization project for jeepneys has two main "blindsides," according to information gathered from drivers and operators as well as data: the high cost of each new jeepney and the potential ripple effect of raising jeepney fares to offset the cost of buying new jeepney units. Jeepney drivers fear that the modernization initiative would risk their means of support. Many are concerned that newer, more expensive modernized jeepneys would displace them or make them less relevant because they have dedicated their life to this line of work. According to Atos et al. (2021), the country's historical symbol, the jeepney, was one of the programs that was modernized. Cabin operators, drivers, and commuters were all impacted by the jeepney's upgrades. In addition, according to Savilla et al. (2024). In general, drivers disagreed with the program's implementation and opposed its execution. Some drivers feel left out by government policies that prioritize modernization without properly taking seriously the opinions of drivers or listening to their concerns.

Theme 2: The Impact of Jeepney Modernization on Fare, Affordability, Job Security, and Route Adjustments

The modernization of jeepneys in the Philippines has had a significant influence on both drivers and commuters. As the government pushes for the transition to more modern and environmentally friendly vehicles, drivers are faced with affordability issues and potential debt accumulation. According to Manuel (2019), the jeepney phase-out will impose a significant financial strain on drivers and operators. The government is set to require them to invest in new electric jeepneys, demanding substantial down payments running into hundreds of thousands. The cost of upgrading to modern jeepneys poses a financial challenge for many drivers, leading to concerns about their livelihoods and financial stability. This shift towards modernization also raises job insecurity among drivers, as the transition may result in reduced demand for traditional jeepneys, potentially leading to job losses and uncertainty in the industry. Furthermore, the modernization of jeepneys could

bring about changes in routes that may impact passenger pickups and drop-offs, as well as potential fare increases. With the introduction of modernized jeepneys and potential adjustments to existing routes, commuters may experience disruptions in their daily commute patterns. Changes in routes could affect the accessibility of certain areas and the convenience of transportation for passengers.

Subtheme 2.1: Implications and Effects of the Fare Increase on Jeepney Drivers and Commuters.

This sub-theme comes up as a major problem in fare adjustment with public transit and commuting. The daily lives of commuters are affected by the hike in passenger and jeepney fares, especially those who depend on these forms of transportation for their daily commute. According to Piquero (2024), “Regular commuters will have a much harder time finding their monthly expenses since, should the Public Utility Vehicle Modernization (PUVM) initiative be completely executed, jeepney drivers will likely demand higher minimum fares—which could rise by as much as P25.” As stated by Agpaoa (2024), “Leaders in the transport sector have cautioned that the minimum ticket, which is currently P15, will increase to P40 if the Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program (PUVMP) is completely implemented.” In addition, according to Yu (2024), commuters may suffer because of the government's modernization effort, as minimum tariffs could rise from the current P15 to as much as P40. Due to the high cost of modern jeepneys, experts and manufacturers are concerned that fares may need to be increased. This is especially true since some operators are already having trouble affording the monthly amortization of their new cars.

Subtheme 2.2: Affordability Issues for Drivers and Potential Debt Accumulation.

The financial challenges that jeepney drivers face, especially considering the ongoing modernization initiatives, have the potential to lead to the accumulation of significant levels of debt, creating a pressing financial burden for those individuals working in the jeepney industry. According to Fernandez (2019), current e-jeepney costs at least PHP 1.2 million (about USD 23,400), therefore switching to one requires a significant upfront expense. Operators must comply with a regulatory mandate of owning at least 10 units, further increasing the financial strain. This significant initial expense has raised significant worries among operators and drivers.

Operators and drivers in the jeepney industry are raising concerns about the substantial upfront costs associated with purchasing modern jeepneys. The shift towards these advanced and eco-friendly vehicles has notably heightened the financial burden on individuals within the sector, making it more challenging for them to adapt to the changing dynamics of public transportation. Bautista & Moya (2023) stated that on average, a jeepney operator generates a daily gross income ranging from P2,500 to P3,000. But due to costs like fuel, maintenance, and compensation to the jeepney driver (typically about P500), this income is drastically decreased. The cost of a modern jeepney far surpasses that of a traditional one, posing a substantial financial challenge for jeepney drivers and operators. The increased costs of transitioning to modern jeepneys in comparison to traditional ones create a notable financial obstacle for jeepney drivers and operators. This

significant difference in expenses highlights the financial constraints faced by those in the industry, adding complexity to their ability to adjust to the changing dynamics of public transportation.

Subtheme 2.3: Competition Among Traditional and Modern Jeepneys for Passengers Based on Comfort Preferences.

The transition to modern jeepneys poses a formidable challenge regarding job insecurity for traditional jeepney drivers. The transition to modern jeepneys has the potential to decrease the demand for traditional jeepneys, leading to potential job losses and industry instability. Drivers are confronted with the imminent risk of losing their primary source of income. As stated by Malasique et al. (2022), the Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program (PUVMP) influences PUV drivers' employment because it creates new job opportunities while also removing their existing sources of income. The shift from traditional jeepneys to modernized ones and the requirement to obtain valid franchises present financial hurdles that not all PUV drivers can overcome. The problem is made worse by difficulties in merging with firms or cooperatives, which has a big impact on PUV drivers' employment in the Philippines. In addition, Manuel (2019) expressed concerns about the potential phase-out of jeepneys and its implications for drivers and operators. These individuals rely on driving jeepneys for their livelihood, supporting their families and children's education. The disappearance of jeepneys would create uncertainty and financial difficulties in meeting daily needs, significantly impacting their lives and livelihoods.

Subtheme 2.4: Potential Changes in Routes Affecting Passenger Pickups.

This sub-theme surfaced as a possible investigation of how route changes affect passenger pickups. According to Mercurio (2021), the Passenger Forum (TPF), a consumer advocacy group, claims that there is still work to be done on the issue of how different transportation options and routes are connected. As mentioned by About Philippines (2023), "The restricted seating capacity, absence of marked stops, and unregulated rates of traditional jeepneys are frequent points of contention. It is suggested that transportation efficiency and convenience can be greatly increased by introducing larger-capacity, standardized vehicles and creating regular routes. By reducing travel times and relieving traffic congestion, these modifications may improve commuters' general quality of life and productivity." In addition, Yu (2024) stated before the revised deadline of April 30, that almost 1,900 UV Express and jeepney routes ran the risk of disappearing nationally by February 1. A memo circular issued by the Land Transportation Franchising and Regulation Board (LTFRB) states that jeepneys operating on specific routes—including those with low consolidation rates—had until January 31 to resume operations if they were unable to consolidate by the deadline of December 31, 2023. However, there were other routes where no cooperative or company was created by any of the UV Express units or jeepneys operating on them. Under the LTFRB data, 108 UV Express routes and 395 jeepney routes in Metro Manila do not have consolidated organizations. There are 1,948 PUV routes without consolidated organizations throughout the entire country.

Theme 3: Daily Impacts: Effect of PUVM on Jeepney Drivers Daily Lives

There are several negative effects that the Public Utility Vehicle Modernization (PUVM) adoption has on drivers' daily lives. The jeepney drivers face financial difficulties with the necessity to surrender their jobs, and primarily their leaders and the higher-ups because they no longer realize that their freedom to choose is acquired little by little. One of the negative impacts is their financial difficulties. Gumasing et al. (2024) stated that "Jeepney operators and drivers don't make a lot of money because their pay is based on several variables, including passenger traffic, seating capacity, and route profitability." Second, they rely their decisions on the higher-ups because they don't have a choice if the government is the one who implements them. Their freedom to choose is acquired little by little by the higher-ups. Third, the number of jeepney drivers will decrease because some of them will just quit their jobs and others will find another job to be able to support their families. Furthermore, the shortage of jeepney drivers would affect more than just the drivers themselves. According to Recio (2020), "Since low-income jeepney drivers are unable to purchase new cars, the government ought to investigate the initiative. The jeepney drivers would suffer and lose their jobs because of this." In conclusion, the challenge that jeepney drivers face captures the intricate relationship between autonomy and job security in the face of economic upheaval. As stated by Tiglao et al. (2023), disadvantaged locations are densely populated metropolitan environments that are less responsive to changes in transportation networks and physical distance needs, in addition to having a higher number of jobs with lower skill levels. When low-wage workers use public transportation less frequently, they run the risk of being ostracized.

Subtheme 3.1 Freedom of Choice: The Jeepney Driver's Compliance is to Follow the Lead of Higher-Ups.

This sub-theme occurred as the outcome after the interview with the jeepney drivers. Some of them utter that they're just going to follow what the government wants since they can't do anything about it, especially if the government is the one who will implement that program. As stated by Sunio et al (2019) the Department of Transportation is the primary government organization in the Philippines entrusted with developing policies and implementing plans, programs, and projects about transportation. Some of the drivers stated that the jeepney modernization was hard for them but if that government wants it then they don't have a choice but to follow.

In addition, Malasique et al (2022) mention that "Since updating public fleets was the program's primary goal, the government put in place regulations that drivers and public utility operators must abide by". As time passed by, jeepney drivers continuously fought for their rights that's why According to Lu (2024) the licenses allowing independent operators to operate traditional jeepneys came to an end on December 31, 2023. However, this was extended by one month, or until January 31, 2024. This was an extension, the first of which concluded on June 30, 2023. Due to the one-month extension, we expect that traditional jeepneys will no longer run on our routes. Unless that is, the government chooses to prolong the period by which drivers and operators of jeepneys can amalgamate once more.

Subtheme 3.2: Giving Up the Wheel or Seeking a New Path of Journey.

This sub-theme emerges because of the negative impacts of the PUVM on the jeepney drivers. Many jeepney drivers are losing their fate in their jobs because they are scared to lose their franchise and won't be able to drive a jeep again also due to the high price of modernized jeeps. As a result of that they are planning to find a more secure job that can afford their daily expenses. As mentioned by Gatarin (2024), because of the sudden loss of their vital jeepney and source of income, the Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program (PUVMP) is a sensitive and divisive matter in this case.

In addition, according to Guno et al. (2021), Jeepney drivers are forced to live in a city that is created by the capitalist corporate class and the public transportation system because of the "tyranny of the market," which eliminates the human aspect of essential improvements in the jeepney sector through a technofix approach. Because of the jeepney drivers leaving and their jobs being stolen from them because of removing their franchise, it could be the result of a domino effect where not only jeepney drivers will experience it but also commuters and the economy of the country. As stated by Malasique & Rosete (2022), "When transportation networks are not reliable or have insufficient capacity, it can lead to lost or reduced quality of life and lost opportunity."

Subtheme 3.3: Financial Struggles of Owning a Modernized Jeepney.

This sub-theme emerged because of interviewing the jeepney drivers. Many of them are scared that they cannot pay for the modernized jeep until their old age because of their lack of money to buy and maintain the modernized jeep. According to Guno et al. (2021), the abrupt price increases for the already expensive jeepneys are closely related to worries regarding the contemporary model. A 2018 only cost between PHP 1.4 and 1.6 million upon launch. In 2020, this expense is expected to increase to 2.5–2.6 million PHP. But some of the jeepney drivers will allow the jeepney modernization program if the government will help them and loan for them, but when the monthly payment is so high that they cannot afford it, they will be against the PUVM.

In addition, as mentioned by Andalecio et al. (2020), "the chairwoman asserted that drivers of jeepneys who could not afford to buy the updated jeepney received financial assistance from the government in the form of loans." Moreover, Guno et al. (2021) mentioned that high interest rates will compound the high annual payments resulting from high unit prices. At six percent interest, annual amortization costs rise by 25 percent. That's why, according to Andalecio et al. (2020), half of the jeepney drivers said this initiative was presented at the appropriate time and cost, and the other half said the Philippines is not prepared for jeepney modernization.

Conclusions

From the findings of the study, the following conclusions were derived:

1. Concerns regarding the government's modernization measures are voiced by Filipino jeepney drivers, who worry about potential effects on their livelihoods, job loss, affordability, and the cultural value of traditional jeepneys.
2. Jeepney drivers in the Philippines express worries about the strict financial restrictions imposed on modernization, including the high cost of replacing traditional jeepneys and the potential impact on passengers, as well as concerns about route modifications and passenger changes.
3. Jeepney drivers' express resignation and fear of losing their source of income if the modernization program is fully implemented. They fear job loss and future work opportunities, while the affordability of modern jeepneys is a major concern.

Recommendations

1. Drivers may consider investigating other financial options or obtaining assistance from applicable government programs targeted at easing the transition to modernized vehicles, they should engage in advocacy activities to ensure that the government gives enough aid to individuals experiencing financial barriers to adopting newer automobiles, drivers should also be abreast of any update in-vehicle modernization policies and participate in conversations and decision-making processes that affect their livelihoods.
2. Commuters should consider launching public campaigns, utilizing social media platforms effectively and actively engaging with local communities to raise awareness, support jeepney drivers and ensure that their voices are heard, conduct surveys, organize public forums, and establish feedback mechanisms. Commuters should advocate fair treatment of jeepney drivers and commuters alike.
3. Policymakers should acknowledge the perceptions of jeepney drivers when formulating policies towards the jeepney modernization program, policymakers, drivers, commuters and relevant stakeholders should collaborate to develop policies and regulations to consider the welfare of both jeepney drivers and commuters balancing the safety, affordability, and sustainability of both parties and ensure that the regulations are fair and equitable for all the stakeholders involved.
4. Transportation agencies should make use of strategies including frequent meetings, consultations, and easily available avenues for feedback to foster open communication, address driver issues, obtain insightful advice, actively monitor the execution of the modernization program, and conduct thorough evaluations of its effect on both jeepney drivers and the commuting public, to recognize the difficulties of the jeepney drivers with the jeepney modernization program.
5. Future Researchers should use this as a guide and as a reference for their academic pursuits, to pinpoint any gaps in existing research and delve deeper into areas that demand further investigation concerning the viewpoints of jeepney drivers on the modernization initiative and have a deep understanding about the perceptions of the participants and hear their voices about the modernization program.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research strictly adheres to the ethical standards set by the institution and the body of knowledge. All information and data coming from the respondents are solely for

academic purposes only. In line also with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researchers strictly preserved the anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents.

Acknowledgments

The researchers sincerely thank the Almighty God, who bestowed on them knowledge, strength, and wisdom, along with his divine guidance and love. As well as for being the ultimate source of knowledge, strength, wisdom, guidance, and love. Without their benevolence and grace, the researchers could not have finished the study. Without the following people and organizations' complete permission and support—who openly offered to help in any way they could and promised to see this through to completion—this report and its preparation would not have been possible. To Mr. John Louise M. Marcaida, subject adviser and mentor teacher, thank you for your guidance and mentorship in shaping the Researchers to be responsible researchers, students, and citizens of the school and country. His remarkable teaching, insights, and professionalism have been instrumental in the researcher's success in their research study. The researchers would like to extend their heartfelt gratitude to Mr. Khyle M. Rivera for his invaluable support and guidance throughout their study. The direction the researchers took with their research project was greatly influenced by his openness to share his knowledge and provide helpful criticism. The researchers intend to express gratitude to the Bulaon-San Fernando Jeepney Drivers who participated in a research study and welcomed the researchers with open arms. The Researchers are incredibly grateful for their support and kindness, as the study would not have been possible without their participation. Finally, thanks to the researchers' loving and passionate families and friends for providing a haven and constant moral, physical, and emotional support, which enabled them to complete this study.

REFERENCES

- About Philippines (2023). The Jeepney Phaseout: Balancing Progress and Heritage. Medium. <https://medium.com/@delapenajoevrick/the-jeepney-phaseout-balancing-progress-and-heritage-de3c6443dcfb>.
- Agpaoa, B. F. C., Gallevo, H. M. U., Lasco, R. S. M., Roma, P. A. G., Tan, B. Y., & Vallespin, M. R. (2024). Steering Towards Sustainable Mobility: A Holistic Examination of Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program Impact on Commuting Public and Private School Students in the University Belt, Manila, Philippines. Agpaoa, Brickette, FC, Gallevo, Helena Maria, U., Lasco, Rohann Sherry, M., Roma, Pretty Angel, G., Tan, Blessie, Y., & Vallespin, Mc Rollyn, D.(2024). Steering Towards Sustainable Mobility: A Holistic Examination of Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program Impact on Commuting Public and Pri.
- Andalecio, A. B. P., Aquino, K. E. C., Cruz, C. F. A., De Guzman, A., & Kiong, N. T. C. (2020, April). Implementation, challenges and stakeholders' perception of modernized Jeepneys in Metro Manila. In Journal of Physics: Conference Series (Vol. 1529, No. 3, p. 032067). IOP Publishing.

- Atos, M. S. Q., Cabe, K. H. B., Gomez, C. J. E., & Padupad, C. L. O. (2021). Modernized Tradition: Transformation of Public Transport. https://animorepository.dlsu.edu.ph/conf_shsrescon/2021/paper_spl/2
- Baluyot, M. K., Cuenca, C., Custodio B. P., Jazmines, S. A. E. (2017). B8-4 An Ergonomic Study on the Ideal Interior of Jeepneys Based on Anthropometric Measurements of Filipinos. *The Japanese Journal of Ergonomics*, 53. <https://doi.org/10.5100/jje.53.S64>
- Baracao, E., Casimiro, R., Manuzon, E., & Ramos, V. (2023). Palayan Jeepney Operators and Drivers Association and the Proposed Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program. *The Quest: Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*, 2(3).
- Bautista, N. B. & Moya, R. N. (2023, September 3). Jeepney modernization program: Drivers have a steep price to pay. <https://www.philstar.com/headlines/2023/09/03/2293549/jeepney-modernization-program-drivers-have-steep-price-pay>
- Biona, J. B. M., Lopez, N. S., & Hecita, I. J. (2023). Re-calibrating the Jeepney Modernization Program: Policy Issues and Recommendations. <https://www.dlsu-jrig.com/s/Recalibrating-the-Jeepney-Modernization-Program.pdf>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2) 77-101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>.
- Castro, R. L. (2019). The Philippine Jeepney: A Symbol of Philippine Culture and Nationalism. *Philippine Sociological Review*, 67(1), 56-76. DOI: 10.1353/psr.2019.0003
- Cerio, C. T. (2017). THE MOTORCYCLE TAXI PHENOMENON IN THE PHILIPPINES: IS THE DEMISE OF JEEPNEY POSSIBLE? *International Journal of Tourism & Hospitality Reviews*, 4(2), 44–52. <https://doi.org/10.18510/ijthr.2017.421>
- Clavecillas, R. C., Bathan, G. M., Maglantay, R. S., Rogelio, J. P., Munsayac, F. E. T., & Baldovino, R. G. (2018). Design and Finite Element Analysis of Customized Local Road Vehicles (CLRV): The Case for the Tricycle and the Philippine Jeepney. In *TENCON 2018-2018 IEEE Region 10 Conference* (pp. 1758-1761). IEEE.
- Department of Science and Technology (2023). DOST TOUTS E-JEEP, LPG-POWERED JEEPS FOR PUJ MODERNIZATION. <https://pcieerd.dost.gov.ph/news/latest-news/513-dost-touts-e-jeep-lpg-powered-jeeps-for-puj-modernization>.
- Dimalanta, R., Atienza, J. M., & Samonte, E. (2019). Putting Transport Workers and Commuters First. <https://cids.up.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/Putting-Transport-Workers-and-Commuters-First-The-Route-to-Just-Transition-in-Public-Transport-Modernization.pdf>
- Estipular, E. J. (2020). Looking into the Implementation of Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program.
- Fernandez, H.A. (2019). Do Filipinos dream of electric jeepneys? *Eco-Business*. <https://www.eco-business.com/news/do-filipinos-dream-of-electric-jeepneys/>
- Gatarin, G. R. (2024, March). Modernizing the 'king of the road': Pathways for just transitions for the Filipino jeepney. *Urban Governance*, 4(1), 37–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ugj.2023.11.0>.

- Gumasing, M. J. J., Ramos, E. D. R., Corpuz, J. N. C., Ofianga, A. J. B., Palad, J. M. R., Urbina, L. G. B., ... & Ong, A. K. S. (2024). Factors Influencing the Adoption of Electric Jeepneys: A Philippine Perspective. *World Electric Vehicle Journal*, 15(7), 284.
- Guno, C. S., A. A. Collera, and C. B. Agaton (2021). "Barriers and Drivers of Transition to Sustainable Public Transport in the Philippines," *World Electric Vehicle Journal*, 12/1 (2021), 46. <https://doi.org/10.3390/wevj12010046>.
- Guno, C. S., Collera, A. A., & Agaton, C. B. (2021). Barriers and drivers of transition to sustainable public transport in the Philippines. *World Electric Vehicle Journal*, 12(1), 46.
- Hennink, M., Hutter, I., & Bailey, A. (2020). *Qualitative Research Methods*. <https://uk.sagepub.com/en-gb/eur/qualitative-research-methods/book242878>
- Kaiser, E. (2023). What is social awareness and how does it foster socialization and empathy?
- Landayan, S. A., Magtanong, A. P., Palma, A. M., Rait, M. J., Ramos, J. C., Villar, A. J., & Vallespin, M. R. (2024). From Routes to Resilience: Exploring Manila Jeepney Drivers' Demographics and Perspectives on Proposed Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program (PUVMP) through Thematic Analysis.
- Lu, B. J. (2024.). Navigating the landscape of jeepney modernization. <https://www.pna.gov.ph/opinion/pieces/813-navigating-the-landscape-of-jeepney-modernization>
- Malasique, A. M. P., Rubio, W., & Rosete, M. A. L. (2022). Analyzing the Implementation of the Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program (PUVMP) to the Employment of PUV Drivers in the Philippines. *Journal of Industrial Engineering & Management Research*, 3(1), 45 - 62. <https://doi.org/10.7777/jiemar.v3i1.250>.
- Manuel, R. (2019). I'm a jeepney driver in the Philippines. Here's what I'm afraid of.
- Mateo-Babiano, I., Recio, R. B., Ashmore, D. P., Guillen, M. D., & Gaspay, S. M. (2020). Formalizing the jeepney industry in the Philippines—A confirmatory thematic analysis of key transitional issues. *Research in transportation economics*, 83, 100839. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.retrec.2020.100839>
- Mendoza, T. C. (2021). Addressing the "Blind Side" of the Government's Jeepney "Modernization" Program (Vol. 2). UP CIDS Discussion Paper. <https://cids.up.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/UP-CIDS-Discussion-Paper-2021-02.pdf>.
- Mercurio, R. (2021). Making public transportation work better for Filipinos. *Philstar.com*. <https://www.google.com/amp/s/www.philstar.com/business/2021/01/18/2071099/making-public-transportation-work-better-filipinos/amp/>
- Obilor, E. I. (2023). Convenience and purposive sampling techniques: Are they the same?
- Piquero, P. (2024). P25 fare increase: Jeepney drivers to demand this hike if... <https://cebudailynews.inquirer.net/571185/p25-fare-increase-jeepney-drivers-to-demand-this-hike-if>
- Quinney, L., Dwyer, T., & Chapman, Y. (2016). Who, where, and how of interviewing peers: Implications for a phenomenological study. *Sage Open*, 6(3), 2158244016659688. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244016659688>

- Ranis, R., Conquilla, J., Buncaras, Z., & Tus, J. (2021). The Jeepney Drivers and Their Lived Experiences During the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Phenomenological Qualitative Study in the Philippines. *International Journal of Advance Research and Innovative Ideas in Education*, 7(1).
<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.14033339.v1>
- Savilla, J. C., Mojica, H. A., Macaya, J. M. R., Reyes, P. A., & Zerda, J. K. G. (2024, April 1). Perception of the Jeepney Drivers on the Jeepney Modernization in Indang, Cavite. *April-May 2024*, 43, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.55529/jmc.43.1.9>
- Solina, A. F. M. (2023). *The (Crooked) Road to Modernity: Analyzing the Socioeconomic*
- Stahl, N. A., & King, J. R. (2020). Expanding approaches for research: Understanding and using trustworthiness in qualitative research. *Journal of Developmental Education*, 44(1), 26-28. <https://jstor.org/stable/45381095>
- Sunio, V., Gaspay, S., Guillen, M. D., Mariano, P., & Mora, R. (2019). Analysis of the public transport modernization via system reconfiguration: The ongoing case in the Philippines. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 130, 1–19.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2019.09.004>.
- Tiglao, N. C. C., Ng, A. C. L., Tacderas, M. A. Y., & Tolentino, N. J. Y. (2023). Crowdsourcing, digital co-production and collaborative governance for modernizing local public transport services: The exemplar of General Santos City, Philippines. *Research in Transportation Economics*, 100, 101328.
- Yu, L. S. (2024). Can jeepney fares stay at P15 after modernization? Experts fear it could double. *Rappler* <https://www.rappler.com/business/jeepney-fare-hike-after-modernization-experts-fear-doub/>
- Zagzebski, L. (2017). What is knowledge? *The Blackwell guide to epistemology*, 92-116. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781405164863>.
- Zulueta, T. M. T., Ong, A. K. S., German, J. D., Gumasing, M. J. J., & Chico, J. C. D. (2024). Implications of the Progression to Sustainable Public Transportation: An Insight into Modern Jeepney Shift from the Philippines. *Sustainability*, 16(10), 3912.
-